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**СОЦІАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГІЧНІ АСПЕКТИ ПЕДАГОГІЧНОЇ
КОМУНІКАЦІЇ В УМОВАХ ВІЙНИ**
**SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PEDAGOGICAL
COMMUNICATION IN WARTIME**

В умовах війни педагогічна освітня комунікація виконує важливі функції, такі як забезпечення доступу до навчання та інформації, збереження нормальної психологічної атмосфери в навчальному закладі, зменшення відстані між вчителем та учнем, забезпечення можливості виконання домашніх завдань тощо. Педагогічна комунікація важлива не лише для забезпечення процесу навчання, а й для формування громадської думки, підвищення культурного рівня населення, сприяння соціальній стабільності в країні.

Ключові слова: педагогічна та освітня комунікація, психологічна атмосфера.

In times of war, pedagogical educational communication performs important functions, such as providing access to education and information, maintaining a normal psychological atmosphere in an educational institution, reducing the distance between teacher and student, ensuring the possibility of doing homework, etc. Pedagogical communication is important not only for ensuring the learning process, but also for shaping public opinion, raising the cultural level of the population, and promoting social stability in the country.

Military conflicts have a serious impact on the education system. First of all, they lead to the destruction of schools, colleges, and universities, as well as the evacuation of students and teachers. In Ukraine, a military conflict can lead to a reduction in the education budget, which will lead to a reduction in the number of schools and teachers, a decrease in the quality of education, and an increase in teacher unemployment. In addition, military conflicts can lead to a decline in education and learning in the conflict zone, as they can create dangerous conditions for learning, such as shelling and explosions. In such circumstances, teachers may be forced to work in unsafe conditions, which can lead to a decrease in the quality of learning (Nechitailo I., 2022). On the other hand, military conflicts can also lead to increased interest in education among the population, as they can contribute to the development of national consciousness and patriotism. In this case, education can become a means of improving skills and increasing the chances of getting to know the world outside the conflict.

One of the most important aspects of pedagogical educational communication in wartime is ensuring the safety of the educational process. In a conflict zone, educational institutions can be targeted, so it is necessary to ensure

an adequate level of security in schools and universities, as well as protection from information threats.

Another important aspect is ensuring access to education and information. War conditions can become an obstacle to education, so it is necessary to look for new forms and methods of education, involve various experts and specialists in the educational process, and create conditions for distance learning.

The third aspect is to maintain a normal psychological atmosphere in the educational institution. War conditions can cause stress and anxiety for students and teachers, so it is necessary to create support for the psychological health of all participants in the educational process. This can be done through a variety of activities, such as relaxation training, counseling, yoga or meditation classes. You can also organize special activities to support interpersonal relationships, such as games and team building activities that promote cooperation and joint problem solving ((Nechitailo I., 2022).

In addition, it is important to maintain open communication and provide information about what is happening in the country and the world. This will help avoid rumors and incorrect information that can cause panic and fear among students and teachers. In a time of war, when information can be distorted or even hidden, educational communication is especially important. It helps to disseminate truthful information that allows people to understand the situation and take the necessary steps to protect their own safety and the safety of others. In addition, pedagogical educational communication helps to increase critical thinking and analytical skills, enabling people to make informed choices in difficult situations.

Educational communication can also influence the formation of positive values, such as peace, tolerance, cooperation and cohesion. These values can be reflected in courses and curricula, in interactions with teachers and other stakeholders in the learning process, and in the information materials that are disseminated.

Thus, it can be said that pedagogical educational communication is a key factor in raising public awareness, providing truthful and reliable information, and forming positive values in times of war and conflict. It is one of the most effective means of influencing society, providing information support for military operations, and improving the moral and psychological state of military personnel and civilians.